

EAT A
Rainbow
GAIN THE BENEFITS

Red
Supports
healthy skin

**Yellow/
Orange**
Supports eye
health

Green
Helps lower
risk of heart
disease

**Blue/
Purple**
Improves brain
function and
reduces risk of type
2 diabetes

Dark Red
Helps support
athletic
performance
through increased
oxygen uptake

**White/
Brown**
Helps lower risk of
colon cancer and
other cancers

All fruits and veggies are beneficial to your health. They reduce redness, swelling, and pain (anti-inflammatory) and they help protect your cells (antioxidant) so they protect you against diseases and cancers.

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Baked Veggie Chips

TIME: 30 MINUTES MAKES 7 SERVINGS

Ingredients

- 2 medium beets
- 1 medium russet potato
- 1 medium sweet potato
- 1 medium parsnip
- 2 tablespoons canola oil
- 1/2 teaspoon salt
- 1/2 teaspoon garlic powder
- 1/2 teaspoon dried oregano
- Dash of ground black pepper

Equipment

- Vegetable Peeler
- Kitchen Knife
- Cutting Board
- Paper Towel
- Heatproof Tongs
- 2 Baking Pans
- 2 Baking Racks
- Oven

Instructions

- Preheat oven to 375 degrees Fahrenheit.
- Peel beets, russet potato, sweet potato, and parsnip. Cut all veggies into 1/8th inch thick slices (As thick as two stacked quarters). Sprinkle extra salt on the beets and let them rest for 15 minutes. Then pat them dry with a paper towel before adding to the bowl.
- Place sliced veggies in bowl and coat with canola oil. Add salt, garlic powder, dried oregano, and ground black pepper to bowl and toss to coat.
- Place a baking rack upon each baking pan. Then arrange chips on baking racks into a single layer.
- Bake for ten minutes. Remove pans from heat and turn each chip with heatproof tongs. Return to oven and bake for an additional 5-10 minutes or until golden brown.
- Substitutions: Any root vegetable such as carrots, zucchini, and yellow squash can be used. Because squash and zucchini have a lot of water, treat them the same way as the beets. Feel free to switch out the spices listed for any other spices you have on hand. The combinations are endless!

Other helpful resources: www.eatright.org/recipes | www.myplate.org/eattherainbow